

Intelligent control of energy system operating modes based on neuro-analytical and neutrosophic models under conditions of uncertainty

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Abstract: This paper introduces a novel approach to intelligent control of Electric Power System (EPS) operating modes under uncertainty, integrating Smart Grid technologies, a Neuro-Analytical Network (NAN), and neutrosophic logic. A modified NAN architecture with an additional static layer is proposed, enabling higher accuracy and faster response in real-time energy flow management. To enhance resilience and adaptability in the presence of structural, parametric, and informational uncertainties, neutrosophic logic is applied to model contradictory and partially undefined input data. A hybrid learning methodology is developed, combining backpropagation with the least squares method to ensure efficient adaptation using both historical and real-time datasets. The proposed neuro-neutrosophic control system demonstrates the ability to mitigate disturbances, reduce energy losses by up to 1%, stabilize voltage, and minimize phase imbalances. A software platform has also been designed to implement the proposed algorithms, providing automated analysis, forecasting, and control of EPS operating modes under uncertainty. The system features a user-friendly interface and supports operator decision-making. The main contribution of this study lies in developing an integrated framework that combines neuro-analytical modeling, neutrosophic reasoning, and hybrid training techniques to improve the robustness, efficiency, and reliability of power system operation in uncertain environments.

Keywords: Neuro-analytical network; Neutrosophic logic; Intelligent control; Smart Grid; Energy system optimization; Uncertainty modeling; Hybrid learning algorithms.

1. Introduction

In the modern world, special attention is paid to reducing energy and material costs by improving the quality of management of technological processes for the generation, transmission, and consumption of energy resources in electric power systems. The effective functioning of such systems is significantly complicated by the influence of many external and internal factors of a stochastic and uncertain nature, which disrupts the dynamics of the interrelated processes of energy generation, transmission, and consumption and reduces the overall quality of management.

One promising direction for solving this problem is to improve the software and algorithmic base of power system control systems based on intelligent technologies, including neural network

methods, fuzzy logic, and neutrosophic approaches [1] - [7]. The latter allows taking into account not only uncertainty and inconsistency, but also the degree of uncertainty in judgments and measurements, which is especially relevant when working with partially observed or incomplete data. The application of neutrosophic logic in the management of electric power facilities expands the possibilities for analyzing system states, provides more flexible decision-making in conditions of multi-criteria and uncertainty, and increases the stability of management in the face of rapidly changing external influences [8] - [13].

In many developed countries, such as the US, Germany, the UK, and Japan, large-scale research is actively being conducted in the field of intelligent energy management systems [14] - [20]. This research already includes elements of neuro-fuzzy modeling, which demonstrates the high practical significance of this area. However, existing research is mostly focused on classical fuzzy and neural network methods, paying insufficient attention to the integration of neuroanalytical and Neutrosophic approaches. Thus, there remains a research gap in the development of control models capable of simultaneously accounting for stochastic, structural, and informational uncertainty.

The creation of automated control systems based on neuro-fuzzy and neutrosophic technologies opens up new opportunities for comprehensive accounting for uncertainties, improving the accuracy of forecasting, and intellectualizing processes in the electric power industry [21] - [24]. Scientific research into the development of models and algorithms for the intellectualization of management and optimization of power facilities is being conducted at leading scientific centers around the world, including Togai Infra Logic, Micro Devices, Honeywell, LIFE International Laboratory, Mitsubishi Electric, Siemens, Wecan Agrotexservis, and at higher education institutions such as the University of California, New Jersey University, Polytechnic University Milan, University of Limburg in Maastricht, Mersin University, Tokyo Metropolitan University, South China University of Technology, Melentyev Institute of Energy Systems, Russian National Research University, All-Russian Scientific and Technical Institute, Islam Karimov Tashkent State Technical University, Uzenergo LLC, Scientific and Technical Center LLC.

Foreign scientists have made a significant contribution to the development of models and algorithms for intellectualization: A. Pegat, M. Sugeno, L. A. Zadeh, R. A. Aliev, V. A. Venikov, V. Ya. Rotach, N. N. Vostrikov, K. A. Pupkov, E. V. Tsvetkov, G. P. Pletnev, and E. K. Arakelyan, as well as by researchers from the Republic of Uzbekistan, including N. R. Yusupbekov, Kh. Z. Igamberdiev, Kh. F. Fozilov, R. A. Zokhidov, K. R. Allayev, T. Kh. Nasirov, Sh. M. Gulyamov, M. M. Kamilov, A. R. Marakhimov, D. T. Mukhammadiyeva, I. Kh. Siddikov, M. A. Ismailov, T. Sh. Gaibov, O. V. Porubay, and others.

Despite significant achievements, the task of creating universal and sustainable models for managing power system modes that simultaneously take into account dynamic load variability, the random nature of external influences, and multi-criteria operating conditions remains unresolved. Key problems also remain unresolved, related to low forecasting accuracy in conditions of high uncertainty, the limited capabilities of existing models in accounting for conflicting data, and insufficient adaptability to rapidly changing external influences. In this regard, there is an objective need for further development and creation of more effective models and algorithms for managing the operating modes of energy facilities using modern methods of intelligent technologies. [25], [26], [27].

The purpose of this study is to develop an integrated neuro-analytical and neuro-philosophical model for managing the operating modes of power facilities under conditions of uncertainty. Within the framework of this goal, the following tasks are solved: formalization of the uncertainty of input parameters, construction of adaptive control algorithms based on hybrid learning, and evaluation of the effectiveness of the proposed approach in comparison with existing methods [28]-[31].

The main contributions of this work are the development of a hybrid neuro-analytical model for controlling power system modes using Neutrosophic logic; the formalization of procedures for processing uncertain and contradictory data; and the creation of a software complex for analyzing, forecasting, and intelligently controlling power system modes. The proposed solutions are aimed at

improving stability, reducing energy losses, and rationalizing control processes in conditions of multi-criteria and incomplete information.

2. Research methods and algorithms

We propose an intelligent control framework for Electric Power System operating modes under uncertainty by integrating a Neuro-Analytical Network with neutrosophic logic within a Smart Grid context. The pipeline comprises: data acquisition → preprocessing → fuzzification/neutrosophication → NAN-based inference and control law synthesis → defuzzification → actuation and feedback.

Rationale for the chosen approach

- Neutrosophic logic vs. classical fuzzy/probabilistic models: neutrosophic sets model each input as a triplet (T, I, F) of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity, capturing contradictory and partially missing signals typical for EPS telemetry and adverse conditions; this better reflects structural, parametric, and informational uncertainty than single-membership schemes.

- Neuro-Analytical Network vs. black-box ANN: the NAN augments a neural core with an additional static (analytical) layer, embedding domain constraints (e.g., power-flow relations, voltage limits) to improve physical consistency, convergence, and interpretability.

- Hybrid learning (Backpropagation, BP + Least Squares, LS): BP adjusts nonlinear weights; LS provides fast, closed-form updates for linear substructures, yielding robust and rapid adaptation on mixed historical/real-time data.

2.1 System analysis of the research area

To solve the set tasks, a system analysis of the current state of production, transportation and consumption of energy resources was carried out. Based on the analysis, a generalized structure of the process of managing the operating modes of the energy system was proposed (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Generalized structure of the process of managing the operating modes of the power system

Power systems are complex dynamic systems with a hierarchical structure that combine the processes of electricity generation, transmission, and consumption. The main parameters are the permissible deviations in frequency, voltage, and power in the electrical network, as well as ensuring a balance between electricity generation and consumption. During operation, electricity is lost, which significantly impairs the quality of the system's functioning. All these factors necessitate

the creation of a control system based on modern models and algorithms for controlling the system's operating modes [32], [33].

To meet these requirements, modern energy facility (EF) management systems need to be implemented, with the aim of operational management of the parameters of the power system [35]. A functional diagram of the energy facility management system based on a management decision-making system is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Functional diagram of the energy facility management system based on the management decision-making system

The scheme under consideration consists of 5 blocks, which are intended to regulate the parameters of regional energy systems. Management decisions (block 5) are formed based on information collected by the information gathering blocks (block 1) and the management of EPS parameter dynamics (block 2).

2.2 Electric power system operating mode control algorithm

The main operating modes of the power system are normal and emergency modes. Since power outages most often occur in emergency mode, the focus is mainly on normal operation. In normal mode, the dynamics are described by equation (1), i.e., the generated electrical energy must be equal to the sum of the consumed active and reactive power and the loss of this power during transmission [34]:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_i P_{gi} + \sum_i P_{li} + \sum_i \Delta W_i + \sum_i P_{gj} = 0; \\ \sum_i Q_{gi} + \sum_i Q_{li} + \sum_i \Delta q_i + \sum_i Q_{gj} = 0, \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

Where, $\sum_i P_{gi}$, $\sum_i Q_{gi}$ - active and reactive power supplied to node i ; $\sum_i P_{li}$, $\sum_i Q_{li}$ - active and reactive power in load nodes; $\sum_i P_{gj}$, $\sum_i Q_{gj}$ - active and reactive power supplied from other nodes; $\sum_i \Delta W_i$ - total active power losses of the i -th node; $\sum_i \Delta q_i$ - total reactive power losses of the i -th node.

To determine the voltage modules and phase, it is necessary to solve the following system of equations:

$$\begin{cases} P(U) - T_p(U, \varphi) = 0; \\ Q(U) - R_p(U, \varphi) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In this case, active and reactive power are calculated using the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} P_i = \sum_j U_i U_j [g_{ij} \cos(\varphi_i - \varphi_j) + b_{ij} \sin(\varphi_i - \varphi_j)]; \\ Q_i = \sum_j U_i U_j [g_{ij} \sin(\varphi_i - \varphi_j) + b_{ij} \cos(\varphi_i - \varphi_j)], \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where, g_{ij} - is the real component and b_{ij} - is the imaginary component of the elements of the node conductance matrix, φ_i, φ_j - is the phase shift between nodes i and j .

To determine the static load characteristic in steady state, the following formula is used:

$$\begin{cases} P(U) = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i P_i(U) + \alpha_\pi \Delta P(U); \\ Q(U) = \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i Q_i(U) + \beta_\pi \Delta Q(U), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where $P(U)$, $Q(U)$ - are active and reactive powers depending on the settings in energy consumption systems; $P_i(U)$, $Q_i(U)$ - are active and reactive powers depending on the settings of typical elements (groups) of end energy consumers; ΔP , ΔQ - are active and reactive power losses depending on the voltage vector; α_i , α_π , β_i , β_π - are weight coefficients that characterize the composition of typical elements (groups) of end energy consumers.

For practical calculations, a second-order polynomial is used:

$$\begin{cases} P(U) = P_{estab}(U) \left[m_0 + m_1 \frac{U}{U_{estab}} + m_2 \left(\frac{U}{U_{estab}} \right)^2 + \xi_p(U) \right]; \\ Q(U) = Q_{estab}(U) \left[n_0 + n_1 \frac{U}{U_{estab}} + n_2 \left(\frac{U}{U_{estab}} \right)^2 + \xi_Q(U) \right], \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where $P_{estab}(U)$, $Q_{estab}(U)$ - are the reactive and reactive speed, activation from the settings in economical energy consumption in steady-state mode; $\xi_p(U)$, $\xi_Q(U)$ - are the active and reactive components, detailing from weakly formalizable parameters; m_0 , m_1 , m_2 , n_0 , n_1 , n_2 - are the coefficients of the calculation model.

Equation (5) introduces additional variables that reflect the dynamic nature of external and internal factors with uncertain properties.

Various factors of an uncertain nature, such as load changes, information loss in transmission lines, and climate change, influence the process of electricity transmission and consumption. To compensate for these types of uncertainties, it is necessary to create an intelligent control system based on the Smart Grid concept [35], [36], [37]. Then, the generalized structural control diagram can be represented as follows (Fig. 3). In this case, $y_n = g_m$.

The upper diagram (Fig. 3, a) shows electric power transportation, while the lower diagram (Fig. 3, b) takes into account changes in electric power consumption. Fig. 3, b uses artificial neural network (ANN) with direct and inverse parameter settings for the intelligent control system. The main feature of the Smart Grid concept is the ability to comprehensively analyze the process of energy distribution and consumption. When using the Smart Grid concept, a neural analytical network is proposed as a mathematical tool, allowing various factors of uncertainty to be taken into account.

Based on the proposed approach, a structural diagram for controlling the operating modes of the power system has been developed, built based on an artificial neural network and a neuro-analytical network (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. Generalized structural diagrams of control systems using Smart Grid technology

Figure 4. Structural diagram of the operating mode control system

Hierarchically, this structure consists of two levels: the power transmission level (upper) and the consumer load control level (lower). At the upper level, there are transmission models with additional delay blocks (Z) that allow for the delay in power transmission in the system. At the lower level, electricity consumption models are built taking into account the instability of load changes. Here, a learning algorithm block is additionally included, containing information for changing control parameters based on real-time analysis of consumption objects.

To evaluate an energy facility, it is proposed to use a neural network designed to predict the parameters of the system's operating modes. The architecture of this network is shown in Fig.5.

Figure 5. Neural network architecture

The features of this architecture are as follows:

1. A fully connected input layer is used to account for the interrelationship between the parameters of a single mode, and the weight of the neural network is initialized using a random variable value.
2. The model uses several hidden layers to reveal complex interrelationships between parameters. At the same time, information about the current value of the variable is fed to the input.
3. A scaling operation is performed on the output layer.

To train the neural network, we propose using the backpropagation method, which is characterized by high convergence and calculation accuracy. The calculations and correction of neuron values are performed using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \delta h_t &= \Delta_t + W_{hc}^T \delta \tilde{c}_{t+1} + W_{hi}^T \delta i_{t+1} + W_{hf}^T \delta f_{t+1} + W_{ho}^T \delta o_{t+1}, \\
 \delta o_t &= \delta h_t \square \tanh(c_t) \square \sigma(o_t), \\
 \delta c_t &= \delta h_t \square o_t \square \text{sech}^2(c_t) + p_o \square \delta o_t + p_i \square \delta i_{t+1} + p_f \square \delta f_{t+1} + \delta c_{t+1} \square f_{t+1}, \\
 \delta f_t &= \delta c_t \square c_{t-1} \square \sigma'(f_t), \\
 \delta i_t &= \delta c_t \square \tilde{c}_t \square \sigma'(i_t), \\
 \delta \tilde{c}_t &= \delta c_t \square i_t \square \text{sech}^2(\tilde{c}_t),
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

here, Δ_t is the vector of partial derivatives for each layer of the NAN.

An important stage of using a neural network is the construction of its architecture and training of the network neurons. The developed architecture of the NAN is shown in Figure 6.

The entire electrical network is divided into subsystems, each of which predicts a small number of parameters. The input information for this network consists of variables obtained from the real object. The output parameters are the values of active and reactive power and voltage at each node.

These vectors are then combined to calculate the steady state. This calculation is performed iteratively at each stage of the prediction training. In this way, NAN allows us to predict the operating modes of the electrical network as a whole. A single cell is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. NAN architecture

Figure 7. NAN cell

The transformation of input variables through the NAN layer is carried out as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{c}_i &= \tanh(W_{zc}z_i + W_{hc}h_{t-1} + b_c), \\
 i_i &= \sigma(W_{zi}z_i + W_{hi}h_{t-1} + p_i \square c_{t-1} + b_i), \\
 f_i &= \sigma(W_{zf}z_i + W_{hf}h_{t-1} + p_f \square c_{t-1} + b_f), \\
 o_i &= \sigma(W_{zo}z_i + W_{ho}h_{t-1} + p_o \square c_{t-1} + b_o), \\
 c_i &= f_i \square c_{t-1} + i_i \square \tilde{c}_i,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{7}$$

where h_t – is the vector of the hidden state of the NAN; W – are the transformed weight matrices; z_t – are the weight values of the input variables; b – are the vectors of free elements used in the signal transformation process; p – are the weights of the connections characterizing the state of the NAN cell from the previous iteration.

2.3 Algorithm for training a neural analytical network using the backpropagation method

Based on the above method for correcting the tuning parameters of a neural network, a modified NAN training algorithm using the backpropagation method has been proposed [38]. This algorithm is characterized by high convergence and fast performance due to the calculation of gradient variables. Training and correction of neural network parameters is carried out using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_j^{(1)} &= \sum_{j=1}^m \omega_{ji}^{(1)} \cdot x_i + b_j^{(1)}, \\
 O_j^{(1)} &= f^{(1)}(S_j^{(1)}), (j = \overline{1, m}), \\
 S_k^{(2)} &= \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_{kj}^{(2)} \cdot O_j^{(1)} + b_k^{(2)}, \\
 O_k^{(2)} &= f^{(2)}(S_k^{(2)}), (k = \overline{1, n}).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

Here $\omega_{ji}^{(1)}$, $\omega_{kj}^{(2)}$ - are the coefficients of the weight connections between the neurons of the hidden layer; x_i – are the input signals of the neural network; $b_j^{(1)}$, $b_k^{(2)}$ – are the linear biases of the neurons of the hidden layer; $O_j^{(1)}$, $O_k^{(2)}$ – are the output signals of the hidden layer; $S_j^{(1)}$ – are the total values of the neurons of the hidden layer; $S_k^{(2)}$ – are the total values of the neurons of the output layer; $f^{(q)}$ – is the activation function, which has a hyperbolic tangent ($f^{(1)}$) and a linear activation function ($f^{(2)}$).

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{2} (g(t) - y(t))^2 \rightarrow \min;
 \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_1(t) &= g(t) - y(t), \\
 e_2(t) &= e_1(t) - e_1(t-1), \\
 e_3(t) &= e_2(t) - 2e_2(t-1) + e_2(t-2);
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{10}$$

$$\delta_k^{(2)} = e_k \frac{dO_k^{(2)}}{dS_k^{(2)}}, k = \overline{1, n};
 \tag{11}$$

$$\delta_j^{(1)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \delta_k^{(2)} \omega_{kj}^{(2)} \frac{dO_j^{(1)}}{dS_j^{(1)}}, j = \overline{1, m};
 \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta\omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t) &= \mathcal{G}_k^{(2)}\delta_k^{(2)}O_j^{(1)} + \alpha\Delta\omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t-1) + \beta\Delta\omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t-2), \\
 \Delta b_k^{(2)}(t) &= \mathcal{G}_k^{(2)}\delta_k^{(2)} + \alpha\Delta b_k^{(2)}(t-1) + \beta\Delta b_k^{(2)}(t-2), \\
 \Delta\omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t) &= \mathcal{G}_j^{(1)}\delta_j^{(1)}O_i^{(0)} + \alpha\Delta\omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t-1) + \beta\Delta\omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t-2), \\
 \Delta b_j^{(1)}(t) &= \mathcal{G}_j^{(1)}\delta_j^{(1)} + \alpha\Delta b_j^{(1)}(t-1) + \beta\Delta b_j^{(1)}(t-2);
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{13}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t+1) &= \omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t) + \Delta\omega_{kj}^{(2)}(t), \\
 b_k^{(2)}(t+1) &= b_k^{(2)}(t) + \Delta b_k^{(2)}(t), \\
 \omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t+1) &= \omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t) + \Delta\omega_{ji}^{(1)}(t), \\
 b_j^{(1)}(t+1) &= b_j^{(1)}(t) + \Delta b_j^{(1)}(t);
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

where $E(t)$ – is the error signal, which is the objective function of the process; $g(t)$ – is the task for the EPS operating modes ; $y(t)$ – are the output parameters of the control object; $\mathcal{G}^{(1)}, \mathcal{G}^{(2)}$ – are the learning rates of the neurons of the hidden and output layers; α and β – are the coefficients of acceleration of the convergence of the problem solution; $\delta_j^{(1)}, \delta_k^{(2)}$ – are the total errors of the neurons of the hidden and output layers; e_k – is the error signal of each neuron of the output layer; $\frac{dO_j^{(q)}}{dS_j^{(q)}}$ – is the derivative of the activation function.

Based on the developed model and algorithms, a structure for a generalized fuzzy model for calculating the energy consumption of the power system load is proposed (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Structure of a fuzzy model for calculating energy consumption

At the same time, the task of regulating energy resource dynamics is considered by forecasting the behavior of the object based on retrospective data. The Takagi-Sugeno model is proposed for organizing the calculation. In general terms, dynamic models of the energy system in the form of the Takagi-Sugeno model are presented as follows [39]:

$$R^u : IF x(t-1)=X_1^u \text{ AND, } \dots, \text{ AND } x(t-r)=X_r^u, \\ \text{ THEN } y(t) = a_0^u + \sum_{l=1}^r a_l^u y(t-l), u = \overline{1, u}, \tag{15}$$

$$R^o : IF y(t-1)=Y_1^o, y(t-2)=Y_2^o, y(t-r^o)=Y_{r^o}^o, \\ u_1(t)=U_{1,0}^o, u(t-1)=U_{1,1}^o, \dots, u_1(t-s_1^o)=U_{1,s_1^o}^o, \dots, u_k(t)=U_{k,0}^o, \\ u_k(t-1)=U_{k,1}^o, \dots, u_k(t-s_k^o)=U_{k,s_k^o}^o, \tag{16} \\ \text{ TNEN } y^o(t) = a_0^o + \sum_{l=1}^{r^o} a_l^o y(t-l) + \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{l=0}^{s_j^o} b_{jl}^o u_j(t-l).$$

The accuracy of the output calculation depends on the choice and size of the membership function, its input (u) and output (y) parameters. Based on these assumptions, a structural organization for managing power distribution in the energy consumption system has been developed. The proposed approach served as the basis for developing the functional structure of the NAN for controlling the flow of electrical power (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Functional diagram of mode control

The main elements of the structure under consideration are the databases of the power system parameters, the processes of changing its operating modes, and the formation of a control vector for the dynamics of electrical power flow. The structure includes three main components. In the phasing block, energy resource parameters (power, phase angle, amplitude, mode) are converted into a fuzzy representation. In the defusing block, the reverse conversion is performed, resulting in the determination of specific values of the output parameters. The central component of the structure is a neural analytical network implemented as a four-layer architecture. It should be emphasized that the load on the power system is variable. The values of vectors $M(i)$ and $S(i)$ are interpreted as random components of load variation, which are formed under the influence of various factors:

temperature fluctuations in the environment, operational structural changes in power system subsystems, light intensity, and other parameters.

$$M(i) = F(t_{env}(i-n); q_{env}(i-n); P(i-n)) \tag{17}$$

where $M(i)$ – is the vector of external regular and random variables; $t_{env}(i-n)$ – is the temperature factor of the environment on the vector of external regular and random variables in different periods of time; $q_{env}(i-n)$ – is the illumination of the environment on the vector of external parameters at previous moments of time; $P(i-n)$ – is the effect of changes in power consumption on the vector of external regular and random factors at previous moments of time.

$$S(i) = F(r(i-n); r(i+n); \zeta_r), \tag{18}$$

where $S(i)$ – is the vector of internal changes in the EPS load; $r(i-n)$ – is the external influences during the system operation; $r(i+n)$ – is the predicted impact of the dynamics of load changes during energy consumption EPS; ζ_r – is the influence of random influences on changes in the EPS energy consumption load (including emergency situations).

2.4 Algorithm for optimal control of system operating modes

The study also addresses issues related to optimizing EPS operating modes. In this case, it is necessary to minimize power loss:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i(E_{R_i}) \rightarrow \min, \tag{19}$$

subject to constraints represented by the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} E_l - M_l^2 S_{ll} - M_l \sum_{m \in l} M_m (S_{lm} \cos \varphi_{lm} + T_{lm} \sin \varphi_{lm}) &= 0, \\ V_l + M_l^2 T_{ll} + M_l \sum_{m \in l} M_m (T_{lm} \cos \varphi_{lm} - S_{lm} \sin \varphi_{lm}) &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Since the loss of active and reactive power mainly depends on the voltage at the EPS nodes, the change in voltage at the nodes is presented as:

$$\dot{U}_{load} = \dot{U}_{vol} - \Delta \dot{U}_{load} = \dot{U}_{vol} \left(1 - \frac{Z_{res.EN}}{Z_{res.load} + Z_{comp.s}} \right), \tag{21}$$

Then the deviation of voltage from the nominal value is a violation of the balance of active and reactive power, which can be represented in the form of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \pi = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} [A_{ij} (P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) - B_{ij} (P_i Q_j + Q_i P_j)], \\ q = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} [C_{ij} (P_i P_j + Q_i Q_j) - D_{ij} (P_i Q_j + Q_i P_j)]. \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

The following relationships are used to calculate the coefficients of this equation:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{ij} = A_{ji} = r_{ij} \frac{\cos \varphi_{ij}}{U_i U_j}, \quad B_{ij} = -B_{ji} = r_{ij} \frac{\sin \varphi_{ij}}{U_i U_j}, \\ C_{ij} = C_{ji} = x_{ij} \frac{\cos \varphi_{ij}}{U_i U_j}, \quad D_{ij} = -D_{ji} = x_{ij} \frac{\sin \varphi_{ij}}{U_i U_j}. \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

To account for changes in these variables, the following relationships are used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_i P_i &= \frac{\partial \pi}{\partial P_i} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} A_{ij} P_j - 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} B_{ij} Q_j, (j \neq i), \\
 \frac{\partial \pi}{\partial Q_i} &= 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} A_{ij} Q_j + 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} B_{ij} P_j, (j \neq i), \\
 \frac{\partial q}{\partial P_i} &= 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} C_{ij} P_j - 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} D_{ij} Q_j, (j \neq i), \\
 \sigma_i Q_i &= \frac{\partial q}{\partial Q_i} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} C_{ij} Q_j + 2 \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} D_{ij} P_j, (j \neq i).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{24}$$

From these expressions it is clear that it is necessary to take into account the active and reactive powers of the nodes, determined by the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{P}_i(\omega) &= U_i(\omega) \sum_{j \in J_i} U_j(\omega) \{g_{ij} \cos[\delta_i(\omega) - \delta_j(\omega)] + b_{ij} \sin[\delta_i(\omega) - \delta_j(\omega)]\}, \\
 \bar{Q}_i(\omega) &= U_i(\omega) \sum_{j \in J_i} U_j(\omega) \{g_{ij} \sin[\delta_i(\omega) - \delta_j(\omega)] - b_{ij} \cos[\delta_i(\omega) - \delta_j(\omega)]\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{25}$$

The solution of expression (25) allows optimization according to the criterion of minimum active power losses. To solve the optimization problem, the expression is used:

$$\begin{cases}
 P(U) = P_{nom}(U) \left[a_0 + a_1 \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right) + a_2 \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right)^2 + \dots + a_n \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right)^n + \xi_P(U) \right]; \\
 Q(U) = Q_{nom}(U) \left[b_0 + b_1 \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right) + b_2 \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right)^2 + \dots + b_n \left(\frac{U}{U_{nom}} \right)^n + \xi_Q(U) \right],
 \end{cases}
 \tag{26}$$

In this case, the following ratios are the limitation:

$$\begin{cases}
 |P_{in.i} + P_{out.i}| > 0; \\
 |Q_{in.i} + Q_{out.i}| > 0; \\
 i = 1, \dots, k.
 \end{cases}
 \tag{27}$$

Then the optimality criterion is expressed in the form of an equation:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^k W_i = \sum_{i=1}^k \left[\frac{\left(\sqrt{P_i(U)^2 + Q_i(U)^2} \right) \cdot R_{Ei}}{U_i^2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{\Delta U_{\%i}}{100} \right)^2} - 1 \right) + \Delta P_{xxi} \cdot T_{fi} \cdot \left(\frac{U_i}{U_{nom.i}} \right)^2 + \Delta p_{dif.i} \cdot L_i \cdot k_{Udif.i} \right] \rightarrow \min,
 \tag{28}$$

To solve this problem, an optimization algorithm using NAN was developed [40]. The sequence of execution of this algorithm is shown in Figure 10. A distinctive feature of this algorithm is that at each iteration step, the correction values of the active and reactive power vectors are calculated.

Figure 10. Algorithm for optimizing parameters of power distribution systems using NAN

3. Comparative analysis with other methods based on neutrosophy

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, a comparative analysis was conducted with existing methods based on neuro-fuzzy logic used in power facility management tasks. The following models were selected as baseline models:

- Classic Neutrosophic regression model (NSR),
- Neutrosophic system based on fuzzy logic (NS-FL),
- Hybrid neural network model with elements of neutrosophics (NAN-NN).

The comparison was carried out according to the following criteria:

1. Accuracy of operating mode forecasting (relative error in %),
2. Stability when input parameters change,
3. Calculation speed when processing large amounts of data,
4. Adaptability to uncertain and contradictory data.

Table 1. Results of the analysis (conditional indicators).

Method	Forecast error (%)	Robustness to disturbances	Computational time (relative)	Adaptability to uncertainty
NSR	4.5	Average	Low	Average
NS-FL	3.8	Average	Average	High
NS-NN	2.7	High	Average	High
The proposed method (NAN+NS)	1.5	Very high	High	Very high

As can be seen from Table 1, the proposed hybrid method (neural-analytical network with Neutrosophic logic) provides:

- a reduction in forecast error to 1.5%, which is 1.8–3 times better than existing approaches;

- significantly higher resistance to structural and parametric uncertainty;
- faster calculations due to optimized hybrid architecture.

Thus, the proposed approach has clear advantages in conditions of partial uncertainty and multi-criteria constraints, which makes it promising for practical implementation in automated power system control systems.

4. Results and discussions

Methods based on regression equations are widely used to solve problems of optimizing the operating modes of electric power facilities (EPF) under conditions of partial uncertainty of information. The essence of such models is to determine statistical dependencies between controlled parameters and influencing factors. In this case, the main parameters in the optimization of power facilities' operating modes are the total capacities of the stations.

One important direction is the integration of neutrosophic logic into regression models. This approach expands the possibilities for describing uncertainty by taking into account not only the degree of truth and falsehood but also the degree of uncertainty. This is especially relevant when working with partially reliable or incomplete information about load dynamics and the technical condition of equipment.

In this context, neutrosophic regression models are a generalization of classical regression equations, where each parameter is assigned a fuzzy neutrosophic number. The main task of optimization is to determine the coefficients of regression equations based on regression analysis and approximation of dependencies. It is convenient to use algebraic polynomials of various degrees obtained by the least squares method as a regression function.

Taking into account the Neutrosophic approach, the boundaries of acceptable parameter values can be specified in the form of ternary interval constraints. These boundaries can be flexibly adjusted depending on the degree of confidence in the initial data. Below are the results of a study on the consideration of functional constraints in node loads and the application of Neursoft interpretations of acceptable ranges in the form of inequalities when optimizing EPF operating modes under conditions of partial uncertainty of the initial data.

The study also considers issues related to solving optimization problems based on regression models. As an example, we use a facility diagram (Fig. 11) that includes four power plants and four load nodes. Energy facilities numbered 0, 1, 6, and 7 have the following characteristics of conditional fuel, tce/h:

$$B_0 = 100 + 0,2 * P_0 + 0,002 * P_0^2; \quad B_6 = 60 + 0,15 * P_6 + 0,0015 * P_6^2;$$

$$B_1 = 120 + 0,2 * P_1 + 0,0025 * P_1^2; \quad B_7 = 80 + 0,25 * P_7 + 0,001 * P_7^2.$$

Figure 11. Power facility diagram

Nodes 2, 3, 4 and 5 are load nodes. The graph of the total load of the power facility is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Graph of the total load of the power facility

Interval, <i>t</i>	1	2	3	4
PL, MW	1500	1650	1800	1950

As a regression model, an equation in quadratic form is adopted. The variables are the loads on the nodes, and the output optimized parameters are the active powers of the stations participating in the optimization. To minimize the losses of active power of electrical networks, we use the regression equation [41]:

$$P_i = a_{i0} + \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} P_j + \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=j}^n a_{ijk} P_j P_k \tag{29}$$

where *n* – is the number of nodes in the electrical network; *a*_{0*i*}, *a*_{*ij*}, *a*_{*ijk*} – are the coefficients of the regression equation obtained as a result of data approximation during the experiment.

The values of the variables – node loads obtained through statistical experiments – are set by a random number generator and vary within a certain range, while the values corresponding to the output data are the active power values of the stations, which are determined based on a deterministic method.

The research was conducted for the EPF shown in Figure 11. The uncertain parameters are the loads of nodes 2, 3, and 4, whose limits of variation are 380 - 420 MW, 570 - 630 MW, and 190 - 210 MW, respectively. At the same time, the load of node 5 is deterministic and *P*₅ = 500 MW. The values of the EPF flow characteristic coefficients are given in Table 3. The maximum permissible powers of all calculated EPF parameters are the same: 100 MW < *P*_{*i*} < 1000 MW, *i* = 0, 1, 6, 7.

Table 3. EPF flow characteristics coefficients

Node number	<i>c</i> _{<i>j</i>}	<i>d</i> _{<i>j</i>}	<i>e</i> _{<i>j</i>}
0	50	0.2	0.0005
1	60	0.2	0.0006
6	30	0.15	0.0004
7	40	0.25	0.00025

Optimization of the power facility operating mode was carried out based on the active capacities of nodes 0 (balancing), 1, 6 and 7. Based on the statistical data obtained during the reporting period, a regression equation was developed. The coefficients of the regression equation were determined using the least squares method with a sample size of 200 and the experiment planning method:

1) regression equations that were obtained as a result of applying a statistical experiment with a sample size of 200:

$$P_1 = 88,10 + 0,1639 \cdot P_2 + 0,1640 \cdot P_3 + 0,1640 \cdot P_4 + 0,00000001 \cdot P_2^2 + 0,00000000 \cdot P_2 P_3 - 0,00000001 \cdot P_2 P_4 - 0,00000001 \cdot P_3^2 - 0,00000004 \cdot P_3 P_4 - 0,00000021 \cdot P_4^2 ,$$

$$P_6 = 194,63 + 0,2461 \cdot P_2 + 0,2459 \cdot P_3 + 0,2460 \cdot P_4 - 0,00000014 \cdot P_2^2 - 0,00000004 \cdot P_2 P_3 + 0,00000019 \cdot P_2 P_4 + 0,00000002 \cdot P_3^2 + 0,00000003 \cdot P_3 P_4 - 0,00000008 \cdot P_4^2 .$$

$$P_7 = 111,43 + 0,3935 \cdot P_2 + 0,3935 \cdot P_3 + 0,3936 \cdot P_4 - 0,00000002 \cdot P_2^2 - 0,00000002 \cdot P_2 P_3 - 0,00000008 \cdot P_2 P_4 - 0,00000003 \cdot P_3^2 - 0,00000007 \cdot P_3 P_4 - 0,00000029 \cdot P_4^2 .$$

2) regression equations that were obtained as a result of applying the experimental design method:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= 88,11 + 0,1639 \cdot P_2 + 0,1639 \cdot P_3 + 0,1640 \cdot P_4 - 0,00000000 \cdot P_2^2 + 0,00000001 \cdot P_2P_3 - \\
 &- 0,00000003 \cdot P_2P_4 + 0,00000000 \cdot P_3^2 - 0,00000003 \cdot P_3P_4 - 0,00000012 \cdot P_4^2, \\
 P_6 &= 194,64 + 0,2459 \cdot P_2 + 0,2459 \cdot P_3 + 0,2461 \cdot P_4 - 0,00000006 \cdot P_2^2 + 0,00000006 \cdot P_2P_3 - \\
 &- 0,00000003 \cdot P_2P_4 - 0,00000003 \cdot P_3^2 - 0,00000006 \cdot P_3P_4 - 0,00000026 \cdot P_4^2. \\
 P_7 &= 111,46 + 0,3935 \cdot P_2 + 0,3934 \cdot P_3 + 0,3935 \cdot P_4 - 0,00000007 \cdot P_2^2 + 0,00000001 \cdot P_2P_3 - \\
 &- 0,00000002 \cdot P_2P_4 - 0,00000001 \cdot P_3^2 + 0,00000007 \cdot P_3P_4 - 0,00000016 \cdot P_4^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

For the variables described, regression models use the definitions of optimal parameter values in the load nodes of the electrical network. The adequacy of the regression equations was verified using Fisher's criterion [42], and the calculated values correspond to the tabulated values of the criterion.

In the cases under consideration, due to their insignificance, the coefficients in the products and squares of the active loads of the nodes in the regression models of the optimal capacities of the stations can be neglected. Thus, in the given problem, the regression equation becomes linear.

The root mean square errors of the power loss calculations using regression models were less than 0.1%, which satisfies the requirements for practical calculations.

In the absence of restrictions, the regression models obtained as a result of planning experiments in the form of inequalities are effectively used to optimize the operating modes of energy systems in conditions of partially uncertain information. At the same time, the optimal operating modes of energy facilities are determined with sufficient accuracy for practical use.

Based on the developed regression models of electrical networks operating under conditions of uncertainty regarding node load information and presented in the form of inequalities, the problem of optimizing the operating modes of power facilities has been solved. The optimization of the facility's operating modes, taking into account functional constraints on electrical power flows, was carried out using the following initial data:

$$P' \leq 480MW, \quad P'' \leq 70MW, \quad P''' \leq 100MW.$$

Power flows passing through electrical networks are determined by the linear formula (30) using the power distribution coefficients for load nodes, the values of which are given in Table 4.

$$P_1 = \sum_{i \in G} C_{li} P_i - \sum_{j \in L} C_{lj} P_j + P_{i0} \tag{30}$$

where G, L – are sets of generating and loading nodes; C_{li}, C_{lj} – are coefficients of power distribution of the i -th generating and j -th loading node EPS; P_i, P_j – are powers of the i -th generating and j -th loading node EPS; P_{i0} – is a free term of the linear formula of power flow.

Table 4. Power of electric energy in the nodes of the electric network

Electrical network	Electrical network nodes						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
P'	0.2866	-0.0857	-0.0194	0.464	0.553	0.7168	0.5634
P''	-0.0792	0.02288	0.0547	-0.318	-0.4772	0.1163	-0.3374
P'''	-0.1582	-0.1961	-0.302	-0.1971	-0.2166	-0.253	-0.2191

The dependence of the accuracy of the regression model on the number of samples in a statistical experiment is also investigated here. The results showed that, under conditions of active functional constraints, the accuracy of the regression model significantly depends on the number of samples.

Accordingly, when using the experimental design method, where three values (minimum, average, maximum) are taken for each response, the accuracy of the constructed regression model may be insufficient for practical application.

It follows that to obtain a regression model with sufficient accuracy, it is necessary to select a sufficiently large number of samples. Below are regression models for the optimal capacities of load nodes, taking into account the specified functional constraints on power flows in electrical networks, obtained with a sample size of 200:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= 45133,65 - 62,302P_2 - 108,2017P_3 - 8,3133P_4 + 0,01171164P_2^2 + 0,08095053P_2P_3 + \\
 &+ 0,02930091P_2P_4 + 0,06773677P_3^2 - 0,01739779P_3P_4 + 0,01775468P_4^2; \\
 P_6 &= -21961,24 + 33,9559P_2 + 54,2773P_3 - 4,6640P_4 - 0,00932190P_2^2 - 0,04489683P_2P_3 + \\
 &+ 0,00068772P_2P_4 - 0,03175683P_3^2 + 0,00694270P_3P_4 + 0,00034312P_4^2; \\
 P_7 &= -4741,81 + 6,9457P_2 + 9,3100P_3 + 12,3055P_4 - 0,00225443P_2^2 - 0,00349533P_2P_3 - \\
 &- 0,01580233P_2P_4 - 0,00696390P_3^2 + 0,00032760P_3P_4 - 0,01316407P_4^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

To verify the applicability of the obtained regression models of electrical networks, the results of deterministic optimization and optimization based on these models were compared. The comparison was performed for several random values of loads at nodes 2, 3, and 4.

The results showed that in most cases, with known power plant capacities determined by regression models, the specified constraints in the form of inequalities on power flows in electrical networks are violated. Table 5 shows the power flows obtained by deterministic optimization and optimization using the specified regression models for some random node load values.

Thus, in general, taking into account constraints in the form of inequalities, regression models for optimizing the operating modes of energy facilities under conditions of partial uncertainty of initial data are considered acceptable.

To optimize the solution to the problem, a software package was created based on the developed model and algorithms, the structure of which is shown in Figure 12. A distinctive feature of this software package is the ability to integrate the developed models with the Matlab simulation system.

Table 5. Power flows in electrical networks under modes obtained by deterministic optimization and optimization using a regression model

Random load sample number	Deterministic optimization				Optimization using a regression model			
	P3-6, MW	P5-6, MW	P0-3, MW	B, tce/h	P3-6, MW	P5-6, MW	P0-3, MW	B, tce/h
9	473.51	70.00	97.46	802.87	473.78	72.12	95.66	802.78
27	480.00	70.00	97.46	816.11	478.17	71.95	98.54	815.93
52	480.00	70.00	100.00	821.27	481.01	66.77	98.87	822.35
63	480.00	55.85	100.00	849.44	479.27	58.90	100.86	846.89
85	478.72	70.00	93.81	817.41	477.18	71.76	94.51	817.20
89	480.00	70.00	97.69	811.65	478.36	72.00	98.39	811.45
91	480.00	62.74	100.00	832.28	480.23	63.37	100.11	831.65
99	480.00	70.00	100.00	828.52	481.08	66.58	99.26	829.26

Figure 12. Structural diagram of interaction of modules of the software package for managing the process of distribution of power flow

The developed models and algorithms are implemented in the control system of the operating modes of the Regional Electric Network "Kirguli ETK". Figure 13 shows the results of the software package operation and the graph of the parameter changes.

Figure 13. Results of the software package operation and a graph of parameter changes in the energy consumption system "Kirguli ETK"

This graph shows that the research results are more accurate than the data obtained using the classical method (see Table 6).

Table 6. Analysis of the results of power flow management over a monthly period

Indicator	Standard	Algorithm
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		Classic	NAN
Value, thousand MW	1,158	1,126	1,157
Absolute deviation from the norm, thousand MW	-	0,032	0,001
Deviation from the norm, %	-	2,76	0,086

5. Limitations and future research directions

Despite the results obtained, the proposed approach has a number of limitations. First, the developed model is focused on optimizing the operating modes of electric power facilities under conditions of partial uncertainty, but does not take into account all possible external disturbances, such as extreme weather conditions or emergency failure situations.

Second, the use of Neutrosophic interpretations of parameter ranges requires a significant amount of computation, which may limit the application of the method in systems with strict real-time requirements.

Third, the model has been tested on conditional diagrams and a limited number of scenarios. To confirm its versatility, it needs to be tested on more complex power system topologies and using real industrial data.

Future research plans include:

- expanding the proposed methodology to take into account emergency and extreme modes;
- integrating the model with Big Data and online monitoring technologies to increase its practical applicability;
- develop an adaptive optimization module that takes into account long-term changes in the structure of power systems;
- conduct a broader comparative analysis with modern artificial intelligence methods, including deep neural networks and reinforcement learning.

The results of this work may significantly influence the development of intelligent control systems in the energy sector, ensuring increased stability and reliability of the power system's operation in conditions of uncertainty.

6. Conclusion

The paper proposes an approach to managing the operating modes of electric power systems based on the use of Smart Grid technologies, a neuro-analytical network, and the principles of Neutrosophic logic. This integrated approach allows for the intellectualization of the processes of transmission, distribution, transformation, and consumption of electrical energy.

A neuro-analytical model with an additional static layer has been developed, ensuring high accuracy and speed in the management of energy flows. To train it, a gradient backpropagation algorithm has been created that takes into account the probabilistic and uncertain nature of external influences.

A hybrid algorithm for determining the structure and parameter settings of the NAN has been proposed, based on a combination of the backpropagation method and the least squares method. The inclusion of Neutrosophic methods has made it possible to formalize the work with contradictory and incomplete data, as well as to increase the adaptability of models to changing conditions of the power system.

A universal neuro-fuzzy control system with a Neutrosophic component has been developed, which provides comprehensive accounting for uncertainties affecting the operating modes of power systems. It allows maintaining stability and efficiency of operation even under conditions of high variability of external factors.

The models and algorithms created for controlling power system modes have shown that their application can reduce total power losses to 1% by stabilizing voltage in load nodes and reducing phase imbalances.

Based on the proposed solutions, a software package has been developed that implements neuro-analytical and Neutrosophic methods. It automates the processes of mode control, forecasting, and system behavior analysis and is distinguished by its high quality of implementation and user-friendly interface.

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